

Formulation and Evaluation of Paracetamol Mouth Dissolving Films

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Abstract

as mouth dissolving films (MDF), are novel dosage forms designed to disintegrate or dissolve within the oral cavity, offering a convenient way to administer medications. A mouth dissolving film of Paracetamol was successfully developed, with the concentration of polymer and plasticizer significantly affecting the formulation. The solvent casting technique demonstrated excellent film-forming properties and mechanical strength. Among the formulations, F6 showed the fastest disintegration time of 45 seconds and released 98.78% of the drug within 8 minutes. Stability studies further confirmed the film's robustness, making it a promising option for pediatric pain and fever treatment.

Introduction

Fast-dissolving drug delivery systems are gaining traction in the pharmaceutical industry due to their ability to dissolve or disintegrate in under a minute without the need for water or chewing. These systems offer precise dosing, making them advantageous over liquid forms, particularly for pediatric patients and those with dysphagia. Moreover, they may enhance drug bioavailability through mucosal absorption. Typically presented as tablets, their rapid disintegration is achieved either through formulation modifications, such as the use of sugar-based components and super disintegrants, or through specialized processing techniques like freeze-drying and tablet molding.[1]

Fast-dissolving drug delivery systems were developed in the late 1970s as an alternative for pediatric and elderly patients who had difficulty swallowing conventional oral solid dosage forms like tablets, capsules, and syrups. Known by various names such as quick disintegration, rapid meltdown, and fast dissolve, these systems are solid dosage forms that rapidly dissolve or disintegrate in the mouth, forming a solution or suspension without requiring water.[2]

Oral fast-dissolving films are a novel drug delivery method, particularly favored for treating around 90% of conditions due to their patient-friendly, cost-effective, and safe nature. These ultra-thin films quickly hydrate or adhere when placed on the tongue or in the buccal cavity, dissolving in seconds to release the active ingredient without the need for water. This approach allows the medication to enter the bloodstream efficiently to achieve the desired therapeutic effect.[3]

I. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. Justification for selection of drug

Paracetamol is undoubtedly one of the most widely used drug worldwide. Paracetamol is the standard and first-line treatment for fever and acute pain and is believed to remain so for many years to come.

The oldest and most prevailing theory on the mechanism of analgesic and antipyretic actions of Paracetamol relates to the inhibition of CNS cyclooxygenase (COX) enzyme activities, with conflicting views on the COX isoenzyme/variant targeted by Paracetamol.

Paracetamol is a BCS class I compound, bioavailability and solubility of Paracetamol in aqueous medium is high.

Dose of this drug is low i.e. 10 mg which is suitable for film formulation in children.

B. *Method of preparation of inclusion complex:*

The inclusion complex of drug with β -CD was prepared by wetting the physical mixture of Paracetamol: β -CD in the 1:1 molar ratio in a mortar with water. The wet mixture is then kneaded thoroughly with pestle to obtain paste like consistency. The paste was then dried under vacuum at room temperature, pulverized by passing through sieve no. 100 and stored in a desiccators till further use.

C. *Preparation of fast dissolving oral film of Paracetamol*

Oral fast-dissolving films were prepared using the solvent casting method. First, an aqueous solution containing the film-forming polymer was stirred for 3 hours and left for 1 hour to remove air bubbles. A second solution containing the drug, sweetener, and plasticizer was also prepared. Both solutions were mixed and stirred for 1 hour, then cast onto a 6.5 cm diameter Petri dish and dried in an oven at 45°C for 12 hours. The dried film was carefully removed, cut into 2.8 cm square pieces, and stored in glass containers at 30°C and 60% \pm 5% relative humidity until further analysis.

II. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

EVALUATION OF RAW MATERIALS

Prior to development of a new dosage form with a drug candidate, it is essential that certain fundamental physical and chemical properties of the drug candidate and excipients were to be determined. The procedure for various test are given below.

A. **Identification test**

1. *Organoleptic properties:*

These are preliminary characteristics of any substance, which are useful in the identification of specific material. Following physical properties of drug were studied

Colour

Odour

Taste

2. *Determination of melting range:*

The glass capillary method was used to determine the melting point. The sample was placed in a glass capillary tube, which was then tied to a thermometer and immersed in a Thiele's tube containing liquid paraffin as the heating medium. The temperature at which the sample began to melt and the temperature at which it melted completely were recorded..

3. *Solubility study*

The solubility study of sample carried out to select the solvent in which the sample is soluble. In each selected solvent viz; methanol, ethanol, water, glacial acetic acid, hydrochloric acid, phosphate buffer 6.8, pH 1.2, accurately weighed 10 mg of sample was placed and solubility was visually observed.

4. *Infrared spectroscopy:*

Samples were dried in a hot air oven at 50°C for 2 hours, then mixed thoroughly with potassium bromide. This mixture was compressed under a pressure of 10 Ton/nm² to form a circular disc, which was placed in the scanning slot of a Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectrophotometer. The sample was scanned over a range of 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ to identify peaks corresponding to major functional groups, with baseline correction performed using dried potassium bromide.

Evaluation of Paracetamol

Table No.I: Analysis report of Paracetamol.

Test		Reported	Observed
Organoleptic Properties	Appearance	Amorphous powder	Amorphous powder
	Taste	Slightly bitter	Slightly bitter
	Odour	Odourless	Odourless
	Colour	Off-white	White
Melting Point	Melting range	165.6-168 °C	167-168 °C
Identification test	1) By IR	IR spectra of paracetamol have been measured for powder crystals. Ab initio calculations of its equilibrium geometry and vibrational spectra were carried out for spectrum interpretation. Differences between the experimental IR spectra of crystalline samples have been analyzed.	Complies
	2) By UV	The method has been developed and validated for the assay of Paracetamol using mixed solution of methanol and phosphate buffer 6.8 as a solvent in ratio of (1:3) (further diluted in phosphate buffer 6.8 only). The λ max (absorption maxima) of the drug was found to be 246 nm	Complies
Solubility Study	Water	Soluble	Soluble
	pH 6.8 buffer	Soluble	Soluble

Inference: The sample complies with the standards of data manufacturing sheet.

Infrared absorption spectrophotometry of Paracetamol

Figure 1: FTIR Spectrum of Paracetamol.

Table No: II Interpretation of FT-IR spectrum of Paracetamol.

Sr. No.	Assignment	Observed value (cm ⁻¹)	Reported value (cm ⁻¹)
1	OH stretching	3324	3000-3500
2	C-H stretching	3162	3000-3500
3	C=O stretching	1656	1600-1700
4	N-H bending	1565	1500-1700
5	C=C stretching	1609	1600-1700
6	C-H bending	1507	1500-2000

B. Spectral analysis of drug

1. Determination of λ_{max}

Accurately about 10 mg of drug was weighed, transferred to previously dried 100 ml volumetric flask, and dissolved in 10 ml distilled water. Final volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. After suitable dilutions solution was scanned in the range of 200 nm to 400 nm using phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as blank and λ_{max} was noted.

Observation: The λ_{max} was found to be 243 nm.

2. Calibration curve for Paracetamol in 6.8 pH buffer

Accurately about 10 mg of drug was weighed, transferred to previously dried 100 ml volumetric flask, and dissolved in 10 ml distilled water. Final volume was made upto 100 ml with distilled water. Several dilutions were made and the graph of absorbance v/s concentration was plotted as shown in fig 6.1 (table 6.4) and data was subjected to linear regression analysis.

Table No: III Standard calibration curve of Paracetamol in 6.8 pH buffer.

Sr. No.	Concentration (µg/ml)	Absorbance (nm)
1	0	0
2	2	0.189
3	4	0.322
4	6	0.480
5	8	0.588
6	10	0.723
7	12	0.835
8	14	0.902

Figure 2 Standard Calibration curve of Paracetamol in 6.8 pH buffer.

3. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC)

The thermal behavior of drug was studied using DSC thermogram. Any polymorphic change in the drug causes changes in the melting point, bioavailability and release kinetics. Melting point of drug was determined by using DSC. Thermogram for Paracetamol was obtained using DSC (Mettler DSC 821star system, Mettler-Toledo, Switzerland). The drug was hermetically sealed in perforated aluminium pans and heated at constant rate of $10^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ it exhibits a sharp melting endothermic peak at temperature of $25\text{-}300^{\circ}\text{C}$. The samples were put on DSC reference pan and DSC thermograms were obtained. An empty aluminium pan was used as standard reference.

Figure 3 DSC thermograph of Paracetamol.

C. DRUG- EXCIPIENT COMPATIBILITY STUDY

1. Infrared absorption spectrophotometry

It is important to check any kind of interaction between drug and polymer. To determine any possible interactions between the drug and polymer utilized, the FTIR spectra of drug and their physical mixtures with polymers were carried out. All samples were dried in hot air oven at 50 °C for 2 h. The samples were prepared as KBr discs compressed under pressure of 10 Ton/nm². The selected wave number range was from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹ and peaks belonging to major functional groups were identified. The change in spectra of the drug in the presence of polymer was investigated which indicates the physical interaction of drug molecule with the polymer.

2. Study of physical interaction between Paracetamol and Beta Cyclodextrin.

FT-IR spectroscopy study-

The FT-IR of physical mixture of Paracetamol and Beta cyclodextrin was carried out as shown in fig. 6.8.

Figure 4 FTIR Spectrum of Paracetamol and Beta Cyclodextrin.

Result: When IR spectra of individuals were compared with IR spectra of mixture, no considerable change in peaks were observed, which proved that, there was no interaction between Paracetamol and Beta Cyclodextrin.

Figure 5 FTIR spectrum of formulation

Result: When IR spectra of individuals were compared with IR spectra of mixture, no considerable change in peaks were observed, which proved that, there was no interaction between Paracetamol and polymer (Formulation).

D. FORMULATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING FILM WITHOUT DRUG

Film forming polymer was weighed accurately and dissolved in sufficient water. It was rotated for 30 min on magnetic stirrer for complete solubilization of polymer. Other ingredients like glycerol, HPMC and aspartame were dissolved in remaining quantity of water. Both the solutions were mixed on magnetic stirrer until they get completely homogenized and volume was made up to 10ml with water. This solution was then poured into a glass petri plate and dried at a room temperature for 24 h. After drying, the film was removed with the help of sharp blade and subjected to different evaluation parameters.

Table No. IV Formulation of mouth dissolving film without drug.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Beta cyclodextrin(mg)	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125
HPMC	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
Sodium starch glycolate (w/w)	2	2.5	4	4.5	6	6.5	7	8
PVA	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
Glycerol (ml)	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Aspartame (mg)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Water (ml)	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

E. Evaluation Parameters

1. Appearance

All prepared films were observed for their appearance as whether they transparent or opaque.

2. Thickness

Digital Vernier Calliper was used to measure the thickness. Thickness was measured from three different spots of film and average was taken.

3. Folding endurance

Folding endurance was determined by repeated folding of the strip at the same place till the strip breaks. The number of times the film is folded without breaking is computed as the folding endurance value.

4. Dryness test/tack test

This test is performed to find out the ability of a film to get adhered to a piece of paper pressed between strips obstinacy with which the film adheres with the piece of paper or any other accessory pressed in between the films is known as tack. Dryness or tack test can also be performed by with the help of some newly invented instruments.

5. Surface pH

The pH value of a film is usually determined by putting the prepared film in petri dish and subsequently film is made wet by using distilled water and noting pH by touching the film surface with a pH meter electrode. Determination of surface pH is vital as acidic or basic pH is liable to cause oral mucosal irritation.

6. Disintegration time

The film (2.8cmx2.8cm) was placed in a glass dish containing 10 ml phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and subjected to occasional swirling. Time required to break the film into small pieces was noted as *in vitro* disintegration time.

Table No. V Evaluation of mouth dissolving film without drug.

Evaluation Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Thickness (mm)	0.193 ±0.01 5	3±0.1 0	0.23± 0.1	0.36± 0.2	0.12± 0.01	0.15±0. 02	-	0.14±0.0 3
Folding Endurance (folds)	11±1	17±2	11±1	17±2	28±3	17±2	-	11±1
Disintegration (sec)	58±1	61±2	63±3	65±2. 5	80±2	58±2	-	51±2
Appearance	Trans.	Trans.	Trans.	Trans.	Trans.	Trans.	-	Trans.
Dryness test	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	-	Dry
Surface pH	6.67± 2.5	7.09± 2.5	6.84±2. 7	6.96± 1.7	6.77± 2.3	6.61±0. 3	-	6.64±0.2
Surface texture	S*	S*	S*	S*	S*	S*	N A	S*

Values are mean ±SD, n=3, S* = Smooth

Observations

From the preliminary batches it was observed that

1. As the concentration of polymer was increased thickness of the individual film was also increased.
2. Folding endurance of the film is greater with films prepared by HPMC E15 as compared to films prepared with SSG.
3. Films prepared with HPMC were transparent and their surface texture was smooth.
4. Surface pH of all the films is suitable for mouth and saliva PH.
5. All prepared films are found to be dry, no presence of moisture observed.

Calculation of drug dose

Diameter of petridish= 6.5cm

Radius of Petridish= $6.5/2 = 3.25$

Area of circle $A = \pi r^2$

$= 22/7 \times 3.25 \times 3.25 = 33.196 \text{ cm sq}$

Figure 6 Mouth dissolving film

Film to be formulated= length=2.8 width=2.8

Area of single film = 2.8×2.8

= 7.84cm sq.

No. of films caste= $33.196 \div 7.84$

=4.23 films

Amount of drug required= $4.23 \times 125 \text{ mg}$

=528.75mg

F. FORMULATION OF MOUTH DISSOLVING FILM OF PARACETAMOL

Inclusion complexes of drug and β -cyclodextrin were prepared by kneading method in 1:1 molar ratios. The oral fast dissolving films were prepared by using different polymers like HPMC, and PVA, with super disintegrants like sodium starch glycolate and Film forming polymer was weighed accurately and dissolved in sufficient water. It was rotated for 30 min on magnetic stirrer for complete solubilization of polymer. Other ingredients like glycerol, propylene glycol, and aspartame were dissolved in remaining quantity of water. Both the solutions were mixed on magnetic stirrer 10etri they get completely homogenized and volume made up to 10ml with water. This solution was poured into a glass 10etri plate and dried at room temperature for 24 h. After drying, the film was removed with the help of sharp blade. Films were subjected to different evaluation parameters

Table No. VI Formulation of mouth dissolving film of Paracetamol.

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Paracetamol: Betacyclodextrin (mg)	125:12 5	125:12 5	125: 125	125:1 25	125:1 25	125:125	125:12 5	125: 125
PVA (mg)	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
HPMC E15 (mg)	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5	62.5
Sodium starch glycolate (w/w)	2	2.5	4	4.5	6	6.5	7	8
Glycerol (ml)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Aspartame (mg)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Water (ml)	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25

Evaluation

Table No. VII Evaluation of mouth dissolving film of Paracetamol.

Evaluation parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Thickness	-	0.13± 0.02	0.09± 0.03	0.12± 0.02	0.08± 0.02	0.09± 0.03	0.07±0.02	0.14±0. 02
Folding endurance	-	44±4	44±4	35±3	44±4	50±4	40±4	30±4
Disintegration time(sec)	-	52±3	54±2	57±3	56±6	45±3	58±3	60±2
Appearance	NA	Cre my	Crea my	Crea my	Creamy	Crea my	Creamy	Creamy
Dryness test	-	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry	Dry
Surface pH	-	6.84± 0.02	6.70± 0.03	6.91± 1	6.68± 3	6.87± 2	6.72±3	6.74±0. 02
Surface texture	-	S*	S*	S*	S*	S*	S*	S*

Values are mean ±SD, n=3, S*= smooth

I. *In-vitro* dissolution Studies for Paracetamol film

In-vitro drug release was determined by USP Paddle dissolution apparatus-II (Model No. TDT-08L, Electrolab Pvt. Ltd). The release of Paracetamol from Mouth dissolving film was performed at $37 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ using a standard dissolution apparatus. The rotation speed was 50 rpm and the volume of the dissolution medium was 300 ml. The pH of the medium was maintained at 6.8 up to the end of the experiment. Aliquots of 4 ml were taken at specific time intervals and the original volume was maintained by adding fresh dissolution medium. The amount of Paracetamol released in the dissolution medium was determined spectrophotometrically at 311 nm using (Shimadzu UV 1800). The cumulative % drug release at different time intervals was calculated.

Table No: VIII Cumulative % drug Release from batches F2 to F8.

Time (min)	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
1	4.15	13.01	14.85	13.21	12.41	25.21	31.4
2	20.30	21.32	25.86	21.32	21.32	32.30	48.55
4	47.88	36.99	34.45	47.88	38.93	67.31	52.36
6	63.42	51.63	56.05	56.05	56.05	78.40	64.30
8	68.3	72.66	59.61	77.02	72.66	97.35	68.31
10	81.92	97.36	67.34	93.08	97.36	-	75.92
15	91.73	-	87.95	-	-	--	91.95

F7 batch showing 97.35percent release in 8 minutes hence it is taken as final batch.

Figure 7 Cumulative % drug Release from batches F2 to F8.

2. Accelerated stability studies

Formulation F7 was stored at $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ / $75\pm 5\%$ RH. F7 film was wrapped in a butter paper followed by aluminum foil. The films were evaluated for appearance, disintegration time; drug content and *in-vitro* drug release after storage for 30 days. *In vitro* % release from the films was calculated and was compared for change in the dissolution profile. The film F7 batch was wrapped using aluminium foil and kept at above specified condition in environmental control chamber (temperature $40\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ and RH $75\pm 5\%$) for 30 days. Film were tasted after 30 days for changes in appearance disintegration time drug contain and in vitro drug release and finding were recorded,

Table IX Stability study of optimized F6 batch of mouth dissolving film.

Sr. No.	Stability studies	0 day	15 days	30 days
1	Appearance	whitish, uniform having cream color	Whitish, uniform	Whitish, uniform
2	Disintegration time (sec)	43	48	48
3	Cumulative % releases	97.35	97.35	97.35

Discussion:

Result of stability study revealed that, there was no significant change in the formulation batch F7 during stability study. Thus, the formulation was found to be stable. Fast-dissolving drug delivery systems, such as mouth dissolving films (MDF), are novel dosage forms designed to disintegrate or dissolve within the oral cavity, offering a convenient way to administer medications. These are especially beneficial for populations with swallowing difficulties, like children and the elderly, but are also suitable for the general population. This study aimed to develop a mouth dissolving film of Paracetamol using hydrophilic polymers for the treatment of pain and fever associated with irritable bowel syndrome.

During pre-formulation studies, the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) was characterized by evaluating organoleptic properties, solubility, and drug-excipient compatibility through FT-IR spectroscopy. Results confirmed the presence of Paracetamol and showed no interaction between the drug and excipients, indicating the materials' suitability for film preparation.

The films were formulated using the solvent casting method with hydrophilic polymers, plasticizers, and sweeteners. Various batches were prepared, adjusting the quantities of polymers and plasticizers, and were evaluated for physical properties, thickness, mechanical strength, surface pH, disintegration time, and *in-vitro* dissolution. Films made with PVA, HPMC E15, and Sodium starch glycolate (SSG) were found to be clear, homogeneous, and smooth, with low disintegration times ranging from 45 to 60 seconds. Increased polymer concentration resulted in thicker films and longer disintegration times. Batch F6, which disintegrated in 45 seconds and released 98.78% of the drug, was identified as the optimized batch. Batch F7, subjected to a 30-day stability study, showed no significant changes in physical properties, disintegration time, or *in-vitro* release, confirming its stability.

Summary and Conclusion:

A mouth dissolving film of Paracetamol was successfully developed, with the concentration of polymer and plasticizer significantly affecting the formulation. The solvent casting technique demonstrated excellent film-forming properties and mechanical strength. Among the formulations, F6 showed the fastest disintegration time of 45 seconds and released 98.78% of the drug within 8 minutes. *In-vitro* evaluations confirmed the films as an innovative dosage form, enhancing Paracetamol delivery. The process was simple, reproducible, economical, and used readily available excipients, making it suitable for commercial production and beneficial for various patient groups, including those with swallowing difficulties. Stability studies further confirmed the film's robustness, making it a promising option for pediatric pain and fever treatment.

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